

Comparative Analysis of Segmentation Techniques for Different Body Marks

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Abstract

Segmentation is one of the key approaches to image processing. Image processing and pattern recognition is very important. In image segmentation the color and texture of the image plays an important role. Hence the approaches to color segmentation are based on monochrome segmentation strategies that work in different color spaces. In this research paper, comparative analysis of different color segmentation techniques for marks of human body including mole and tattoo. The five segmentation techniques used are active contour, texture, gaussian, k-mean and thresholding. Results obtained in this paper suggest that active contour segmentation technique yields better results than the rest.

Keywords: Segmentation, Color Image, Mole, Tattoo, Active contour.

1. Introduction

Segmentation tends to be essential phase in image processing, a point where it can switch from treating each pixel as an observation unit to dealing with artifacts in the image, made up of several pixels. Segmentation is a technique which is widely used in several different image processing areas. It is the main step in the analysis of images, It can be defined as the process of dividing and separating the region of interest from the image, and plays an important role in many image processing applications. The segmentation methods widely used for the segmentation of images that are histogram, region-based, threshold and color edge-based. If segmentation is performed well, then all other steps of image processing are made easier[1,2] Image segmentation is one of the most important and challenging problems in many applications, such as robot vision, object recognition and medical image processing. While various methodologies [3] for image segmentation have been proposed, this remains a challenge due to overlapping intensities, low image contrast and noise disruption. Area, histogram, threshold, and fuzzy logic[4,16] segmentation methodologies have been widely used in recent decades. While several image segmentation algorithms have been proposed in the literature, they do not generally work well for the specific problem of segmentation of body marks, and it is seems unlikely that any particular method will outperform all other segmentation methods for body marks. Our idea is to take advantage of the fact that the body marks are approximately located in the center of the image during the acquisition process. Along with it, we exploit the color characteristics of the typical marks, and to integrate this information into a reliable framework for the automated segmentation of the body marks. In this paper, we propose (modified) segmentation techniques for segmenting the different

body marks like mole and tattoo using active contour, threshold, k-means clustering, Gaussian model, texture-based.

2. Review of literature

The popular and widely used k-means clustering technique for mole segmentation was proposed, k means algorithm is combined with different methods such as Genetic Algorithm(GA) and Particle Swarm optimization(POS) for segmenting mole. The segmentation is done by employing the output centers from GA or POS as input centers for k-means algorithm. Typically, the number of clustering centers used in the k-means algorithm are 3[5]. The k-means based segmentation technique in [6] employs Gaussian approach to remove noise from the mole image. Authors therein employed 2 clusters; this value represents the pixel within the region of interest that is classified as a part of the healthy skin or the lesion.

Authors in [7] discuss the Otsu color threshold-based segmentation method to segment the mole. It is one of the power full segmentation techniques because it works based on thresholding. Since healthy skin and lesion have different intensities, the method uses them as the threshold level to remove the background skin pixel. Then the foreground lesions are retained and the output image is color segmented.

Along with k-means clustering and Otsu thresholding, [8] discusses Gradient Vector Flow (GVF) to segment the mole area from the image. The initialization of the GVF snake is set automatically and it separates the foreground and background once the snake covers the mole.

Another method for segmentation is the self-generating neural network model (SGNN), which is proposed in [9].The model segments the image as a reference for semi-automatic segmentation or fully automated. The model was developed for dermoscopic image segmentation and was in the position to achieve more definite results below difficult environment than the statistical region merging, fuzzy C-means, k-means and Otsu threshold.

Focusing on lesion segmentation, [10] discusses a lesion detection algorithm which combines edge and thresholding based techniques to detect a lesion from the skin region in an image. Morphological operations are used to select the boundary area of the lesion and then based on the boundary area, the lesion region is extracted from the image. The method proposed therein is compared with Otsu's threshold and Rosin methods for lesion segmentation.

An automated lesion segmentation using a region growing technique is considered in [11, 17]. In order to increase the segmentation accuracy, a median filter is used to remove the edges which are generated by the skin hair. The contrast of the image is increased by histogram equalization and then the region growing technique is applied. Image is segmented based on the finding solidity and extent of the images.

Another automated lesion segmentation method converts the original RGB image to YIQ then luminance channel is extracted from the YIQ image. Uses the average filter to remove the hair from the image. The histogram of the pre-processed luminance channel is evaluated, and the histogram selects an acceptable threshold value. The standard deviation of the preprocessed image is studied and the standard deviation tends to be an optimal value for the selection of the threshold and can be used to automate the threshold for all the images [12].

3. Problem Statement

Figure 1. Segmentation Architecture

4. Methodology

This section presents a detail description of the proposed methods of segmenting the mole and tattoo images as shown in fig.1. The proposed methods have 3 steps, the initial step is acquiring images. Second step is to pre-process the images acquired to improve the image quality and finally, preprocessed images are segmented using various techniques as explained in the subsequent section.

4.1 Image acquisition

Image acquisition is determined as the path about taking or resolving image from camera. It may go through various phases. For the work presented in this paper, some images are acquired from the internet and the rest were captured by Canon 1300D camera with 1.5X to 10X enabled lens zooming capacity and keeping with the object and the camera in a fixed position with a maintain clock word distance between them. All the images were of 300X400 image resolution.

4.2 Image preprocessing

The goal of image preprocessing is to improve the image quality by removing unnecessary distortions and enhancing the image features to further processing. It includes image resizing, hair removal, brightness. Resizing is performed to ensure all the images are at a uniform scale. One of the main functions of pre-processing is noise removal. The raw image obtained may contain hair and air bubbles. These are some of the noises in the image that reduce the accuracy of classification. Hair removal prior to image capturing is not practical in some cases where the lesion is a swollen growth or bleeding. Therefore hair removal in the image using software is necessary. One such effective and accurate software is DullRazor, a medical imaging software. This uses an algorithm based on average filtering. The pixels of the hair in the image are replaced by the neighboring non-hair pixels. It smoothens the images such that the edges and boundaries are preserved, [13]. Filtering plays an important role in image processing to enhance the images through edge detection, sharpening, and noise reduction. Spatial filtering can be performed using the convolution operation as shown in Eq. (1)

$$S(x, y) = \sum_{m=-M/2}^{M/2} \sum_{n=-N/2}^{N/2} h(m, n) f(s - m, y - n) \quad (1)$$

where $h(m, n)$ is the Gaussian filtering mask of size $M \times N$.

4.3 Segmentation

A mole is made up of certain cells which can leave a mark on the skin behind and appear as a defect. The tattoo is an artificial body mark created by the human being. To segment the particular area of the mole and tattoo we propose several segmentation techniques such as K-means clustering, thresholding, Gaussian, active contour, and texture. The next section presents a detail explanation of the proposed techniques.

4.3.1 k-means clustering

There are various clustering algorithms that are developed for a different purposes [14,15,18]. Cluster is a process of dividing the datasets into groups, consisting of similar data points. The point within one cluster as similar as possible whereas point belonging to other cluster are completely different from the point in the first cluster. Clustering is often defining unsupervised learning technique. It is a technique that is based on the gravity centroid of the segment elements represents the cluster. The primary issue of this algorithm is that it sets centroid randomly. These centroids ought to be set in a specialist way in light of the fact that diverse setting causes various results which could be unwanted. One methodology is to put them as distant from one another as could reasonably be expected. The next stage is to take each point being the property of given realities and get it to the closest centroid. When there is no more point to be clustered, the initial step is finished and early group time is finished. Now it is important to re-calculate k new centroids as bar focuses of the bunches coming out of the previous step. Subsequent to getting these k new centroids, another chord is move the focuses to the closest new centroids. When such circle is made, the result of this circle is that the k centroids change their situations iteratively until any longer changes can't be finished. We now summarize the segmentation of the mole and tattoo images k-means clustering in the following algorithm.

Algorithm.1: Segmentation using K-Means Clustering

Input: RGB Image

Output: Image Segmented in color

Start

Step1: Read RGB image

Step2: Set k as the number of clusters.

Step3: Choose the k-cluster centers at random

Step4: Calculate the cluster mean or center

Step5: Calculate the distance between each pixel and the cluster center

Step6: Based on the calculated distance, move the pixel to the nearest center

Step7: Re-evaluate the center.

Step8: Repeat the method until the center doesn't change

Stop

4.3.2 Thresholding based segmentation

Being the simplest and easiest segmentation technique. Thresholding based segmentation transforms a gray scale image into a binary image With the advantage of being fast and easy to compute For effective results, the method requires good contrast between the lesion and surrounding skin. The thresholding-based segmentation technique operates on the premise that the pixels falling within a given range of current values represent one class and the remaining pixels in the image reflect the other class and can be applied locally or globally. For global thresholding the value of the threshold for brightness should be selected to segment image in two regions; one is the object and other as background. The pixels that satisfy the threshold level to be, considered as object pixel are assigned the binary value 1 and all remaining pixels are considered as background

pixel of binary value 0. In our approach to segment the mole area and tattoo area from the mole and tattoo images, since each image contains the different intensity values, the threshold is applied based on the intensity value of mole and tattoo images individually to separate the foreground and background of the images. We summarize the mole and tattoo images segmentation in the following algorithm.

Algorithm.2: Threshold-Based Segmentation

Input: RGB Image

Output: Image Segmented in color

Start

Step 1: Read an image with the RGB

Step 2: Convert RGB image to gray scale image

Step 3: Based on the threshold value, separate the foreground and background

Step 4: Segment the region where the intensity value is greater than the threshold

Step 5: Reshape to the original image

Stop

4.3.3. Gaussian Model

In the method of Gaussian model, based on features of the image or similar criteria of feature set, the image is divided into a series of meaningful and different regions by grouping pixels into clusters. Image is divided into a series of significant and various regions by combining pixels into clusters, it is on features of the image or similar criteria of feature set in the method of Gaussian model. Main nominal features of image analysis, processing and understanding are the consistency of image segmentation and regional boundary accuracy instantly manipulating the following region description and image analysis. Various methods of subtraction of backgrounds and various types of background models to tackle specific challenges have been proposed. Here we addressed the background removal in images with body marks of mole and tattoo using the Gaussian method briefed as follows.

Algorithm.3. Background Removal using Gaussian Model

Input: RGB Image

Output: Segmented RGB image

Start

Step1: Read RGB Image

Step2: Convert the RGB image to gray scale

Step3: Background is set to 1 if the background cover more than fifty percent of the image. Else, it is set to 0

Step4: Separate the foreground and background based on the previous step

Step5: Segment the separated foreground image

Step6: Reshape to the original image

Stop

4.3.4. Active contour segmentation

Active contour is a refinement of an object boundary, we will get a curve formed by connecting their edged points, so there is no clear cut boundary we have to connect those edge points to formed by a curved, then set of connected points, which moves so as to minimize a specified energy function, there is also another name for this one called as a snakes method, the contour over here is actually something which can flow along the different perspectives on the image itself and then it became down to a convergence and from this particular attribute of the contour itself it gets its name called as an active contour. The model is elected as an active model for the segmentation process. First step is we should have an image which is extracted from its background, we will take it as

energy function like gray level value, gradient and initial step is segment a boundary by a general segmentation technique so now we have a object with boundary, next step refine that boundary with technique used wiggle the snake in this it compare the pixel on each point on boundary with energy calculated for point in it neighborhood, it moves the boundary to neighborhood point that has lowest energy and perform the operation once on all points on boundary after that repeat the iteration until it goes no for the movement the process will get stop. Advantages of active contour is computational efficiency and relative simplicity and disadvantage is decision criteria worship complexity. Active contour is used in various field of segmentation based on the application, here we used to segment the body marks such as mole and tattoo.

Algorithm.4.Active contour (Region-based) image segmentation

Input: Original Image

Output: Segmented Color Image

Start:

Step1: Read the Original Image

Step2: Convert the RGB image to gray scale

Step3: Create a Mask

Step4: Initialize the number of iterations

Step5: Set mask with, foreground as=1 and background as=0

Step6: Cover the object of an image based on the region using mask value and the number of iteration.

Step7: Segment the covered area of an image

Step8: Reshape to the original image.

Stop

4.3.5 Texture Based Segmentation (Gabor filter)

The most important step in automatic mole and tattoo detection systems is segmentation of lesion area from the background skin. The images input contain both area of skin and area of lesion. The texture based segmentation method is used for extracting the lesion from the skin surface. Due to its localization in both the spatial frequency domains, Gabor filters can perform multi-resolution decomposition. Segmentation of texture involves simultaneous measurements in the spatial and spatial-frequency domains. In the spatial-frequency domain, filters with smaller bandwidths are more desirable because they allow us to make finer distinctions between different textures. On the other hand, exact location of the texture boundaries includes filters located in the spatial domain. However, the effective width of a filter in the spatial domain and its bandwidth in the spatial-frequency domain are normally inversely related according to the principle of uncertainty.

Algorithm.5. Texture segmentation using Gabor Filters

Input: Original RGB Image

Output: Segmented RGB image

Start

Step1: Read an Original Image

Step2: Convert the RGB Image to gray scale

Step3: Extract Gabor magnitude from the gray scale image

Step4: Post-process the Gabor magnitude image into Gabor features

Step5: Classify Gabor texture features using k-Means

Step6: Repeat k-Means clustering to avoid local minima

Step7: Reshape the clustered image to the original image

Step8: Stop

5. Result and Discussion

On the acquired images, we perform the mole and tattoo segmentation and present our findings in this Section. The segmentation is carried out using the various color segmentation methods described in the previous Section. Based on the properties of each method, mole and tattoos are segmented as follows: Thresholding based segmentation technique works on the threshold value, a variation of the threshold value is based on the intensity value of mole and tattoo presents in the image. This method works efficiently where the image contains a single object. But since in this work the images have been segmented by varying the threshold value, the optimal threshold value for threshold-based segmentation technique was not found for the dataset considered in this work. The k means clustering is one of the effects in segmentation technique, first, it will take several clusters k then it will cluster the near value to given k value. Once the number of clusters is groped then it will find out the mean of the particular cluster. This process will continue until the same mean value comes out from the clusters. This is an efficient method and one of the fast segmentation methods but it totally depends on initialization of k value (number of clusters are initiated). The texture method is also given good results, using a Gabor filtering technique the images are enhanced and depending on the texture the mole and tattoos are separated from the background. This method depends on the theta value for every image that needs to change the theta value. The Gaussian methods flow according to certain image features or similar feature set criteria, it is carried to the pixels on the grouping cluster, and the image is divided into a series of meaningful and different regions. Then it will separate the foreground and background and extract the mole and tattoo. It fails in such a scenario where the intensity values differ in the object. Active contour has given better results compared to the other four methods. Looking at all other circumferences, the active contour segmentation has given near to perfection results. However if the objects with a small loop (closed area), the active contour has not segmented properly. Looking at all the segmentation techniques considered in this work, active contour has given better results compared to others in the case of mole and tattoo shown in below Fig.2 and Fig.3.

Original Image	Active Contour	Thresholding Technique	K-Mean clustering	Texture based	Background Removal using Gaussian Model

Fig: 2. Example of mole segmented images using various segmentation techniques

Original Image	Active Contour	Thresholding Technique	K-Mean Clustering	Texture based	Background Removal using Gaussian Model

Fig.3. Example of tattoo segmented images using various segmentation techniques

6. Conclusion

In this paper we present a comparative study of the various body marks (mole and tattoo) segmentation techniques. Five methods are compared: active contour, k means clustering, texture-based, Gaussian and threshold-based. Each method provides different results based on their setup properties. By analyzing the overall performance of experimental methods for segmentation of mole and tattoo images, active contour technique delivers better outcome. In few cases where the images have an unrelated noise (loops) in the center of the object. In future, we combine active counter with some other high efficacy method to generate hybrid technique to have more precise outcome.

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